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Exploration of Morphological Diversity of Local Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk) in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency, Bengkulu Province as a Source of Superior Germplasm

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Abstract

Jackfruit has advantages as a tropical fruit rich in fiber, vitamins, and antioxidants, and it can be processed into a variety of delicious and nutritious foods. This study aimed to investigate and explore the morphological diversity of local jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk) in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency, Bengkulu Province. A total of 10 jackfruit trees distributed across 6 villages were selected using purposive sampling and analyzed using the jackfruit descriptor published by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI) in 2000. A dendrogram was generated through data analysis using the PBSTAT program. The jackfruit accessions originated from Tunggang (TGG), Pondok Kandang (PK), Lubuk Bento (LB), Karya Mulya (KM), Pondok Suguh (PS), and Air Berau (AB). The results showed two distinct jackfruit groups. Group 1 included Karya Mulya, Lubuk Bento, Air Berau, and Tunggang, characterized by a neat canopy, large fruit size, and moderate sugar content (10–16 °Brix), making them suitable for the development of superior varieties based on fruit size. Meanwhile, Group 2 consisted of two other accessions, namely Pondok Kandang and Pondok Suguh, which produced smaller fruits but had higher sugar content (up to 23 °Brix) and attractive pulp color. Group 1 can be utilized as a genetic source for the development of superior varieties based on fruit size, while Group 2 has potential to be used as a germplasm source for the development of table fruit jackfruit varieties.

Keywords: Accession, Biodiversity, Climate Change, Exotic Fruit.

Introduction

Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk) is a tropical fruit plant belonging to the Moraceae family, characterized by its large fruit size, distinctive aroma, and sweet flavor. This plant grows optimally in tropical climates such as Indonesia. In addition to being adaptable to various environmental conditions, jackfruit can also produce fruit throughout the year if properly managed (Dhakar et al., 2020).

Jackfruit is widely cultivated in several Asian countries, including Thailand, Myanmar, Vietnam, and Indonesia (Ranasinghe et al., 2019). Although the fruit is widely consumed, approximately 60% of its parts such as the rind, seeds, rachis, and perianths are not utilized efficiently and are commonly discarded, potentially

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leading to environmental problems (Khan et al., 2021). The genus *Artocarpus* comprises 38 genera and more than 1,100 species distributed across tropical Asia and, to a lesser extent, subtropical zones (Roy et al., 2018). Several species within this genus have been used as sources of food and traditional medicine (Safitri & Palupi, 2017). Jackfruit seeds are known to contain resistant starch, fiber, and protein, which are beneficial for digestive health and blood sugar regulation (Asmarawati et al., 2014). In addition, they contain active compounds such as flavonoids and also have potential as antioxidants (Buddhisuharto et al., 2021).

The flesh of young jackfruit contains complex carbohydrates and is often used as an alternative food ingredient, such as a vegetable substitute or staple food replacement (Balamaze et al., 2019). Its attractive fruit color and high nutritional content (per 100 grams of fruit contains 95 calories, 23.25 grams of carbohydrates, and 1.72 grams of protein) provide both economic and nutritional value (Gupta et al., 2020).

This fruit can be processed into various products such as chips, toffee, jam, beverages, and traditional desserts (Nurlistyarini & Yuniasih, 2023). Research on morphological characteristics is essential for exploring the diversity of local plants and identifying superior traits as a basis for plant breeding programs (Chandrashekar et al., 2019). Such characterization helps determine accessions with the potential to be developed into high-value, adaptive superior varieties (Gwoykalya et al., 2024). This study aimed to explore the morphological diversity of local jackfruit plants growing in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency, Bengkulu Province. Through a descriptive and cluster analysis approach, this research is expected to provide insights into the potential of local jackfruit germplasm as a genetic resource for future breeding programs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted from July to October 2024. The tools used in this study included a measuring tape, Global Positioning System (GPS), stationery, polybags, knife, bench scale, camera, penetrometer, refractometer, Munsell color chart, ruler, caliper, and digital scale. The research stages consisted of: 1) field survey; 2) determination of sampling locations; 3) monitoring of fruit growth; 4) sample collection; 5) germination and seedling testing; 6) preparation of planting media; and 7) seedling preparation and transplanting.

From July to September 2024, plant growth analysis was carried out in the Wire House of the Agronomy Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Bengkulu. Data collection was conducted on 10 jackfruit trees distributed across 6 villages in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency, Bengkulu Province. These six villages were Pondok Suguh, Pondok Kandang, Air Berau, Lubuk Bento, Tunggang, and Karya Mulya. The accession codes used were: Tunggang (TGG), Pondok Kandang (PK), Lubuk Bento (LB), Karya Mulya (KM), Pondok Suguh (PS), and Air Berau (AB) (Figure 1).

This study employed direct field data collection through observations of the tree, stem, leaves, and fruit. Sampling was conducted purposively. Data were analyzed using the PBSTAT program. The selected jackfruit trees were at least 10 years old, healthy, and capable of producing flowers and fruits.

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Figure 1. Geographical map of the research location for jackfruit cultivation

Morphological characterization of jackfruit was based on the descriptors developed by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI) in 2000. Observations included both qualitative and quantitative traits. The qualitative traits assessed in this study included canopy shape, branching pattern, leaf blade shape, leaf tip shape, leaf color, petiole shape, peduncle position on the fruit, fruit shape, seed shape, pulp shape, skin color, pulp color, and seed coat color. Quantitative traits measured included stem diameter (cm), leaf blade length (cm), leaf width (cm), fruit length (cm), fruit width (cm), fruit diameter (cm), fruit weight (kg), fruit firmness (kgf/cm^2), pulp weight (g), seed weight (g), rind weight (g), total rind weight (kg), fruit skin per kg (kg), perianth length (cm), perianth width (cm), skin thickness (mm), pulp thickness (mm), pulp width (cm), sugar content ($^{\circ}\text{Brix}$), seed hardness millimeter divisions (mld), fruit stalk length (cm), total number of seeds (units), and number of seeds per kg.

RESULTS

There were five types of canopy shapes observed: irregular, semicircular, elliptical, oblong, and broadly pyramidal. Five (5) accessions with irregular canopy shapes originated from Pondok Kandang Village, Tunggang Village, and Lubuk Bento Village; two (2) accessions with semicircular canopy shapes were from Karya Mulya Village and Air Berau Village; one (1) accession with an elliptical canopy shape was from Lubuk Bento Village; one (1) accession with an oblong canopy shape was from Pondok Suguh Village; and one (1) accession with a broadly pyramidal canopy shape was from Karya Mulya Village (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Canopy shape form: (a) Pondok Kandang (irregular) (b) Air Berau (semicircular) (c) Lubuk Bento (elliptical) (d) Pondok Suguh (oblong) (e) Karya Mulya (broadly pyramidal)

There were four types of branching patterns: irregular, horizontal, opposite, and erect. Five (5) accessions with irregular branching patterns originated from three villages: Pondok Kandang, Tunggang, and Lubuk Bento. Two (2) accessions had horizontal branching patterns, originating from Pondok Suguh and Karya Mulya Villages. Two (2) accessions exhibited opposite branching patterns, which were found in accessions from Karya Mulya and Air Berau Villages. One (1) accession with an erect branching pattern was identified in Lubuk Bento Village (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Branching patterns: (a) Tunggang (irregular), (b) Pondok Suguh (horizontal), (c) Air Berau (opposite), (d) Lubuk Bento (erect).

There were three types of leaf blade shapes: narrowly elliptic, broadly elliptic, and elliptic. Six (6) accessions with elliptic leaf shapes originated from five villages: Pondok Suguh, Pondok Kandang, Tunggang, Karya Mulya, and Air Berau. Two (2) accessions with narrowly elliptic leaf shapes came from two villages: Tunggang and Lubuk Bento. Two (2) accessions with broadly elliptic leaf shapes were found in accessions from Karya Mulya and Air Berau Villages (Figure 4).

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Figure 4. Leaf blade shape: (a) Pondok Suguh (elliptic), (b) Tunggang (narrowly elliptic), (c) Air Berau (broadly elliptic)

There were two types of leaf apex shapes: acute and acuminate. Seven (7) accessions with acuminate leaf apex shapes originated from six villages: Pondok Suguh, Pondok Kandang, Karya Mulya, Tunggang, Air Berau, and Lubuk Bento. Three (3) accessions with acute apex shapes came from three villages: Tunggang, Karya Mulya, and Lubuk Bento.

Figure 5. Leaf apex shapes: (a) Tunggang (acute), (b) Air Berau (acuminate)

There were three types of leaf petiole base shapes, namely oblique, rounded, and cuneate. Seven accessions with an oblique base shape were identified, originating from five villages: Pondok Kandang, Tunggang, Karya Mulya, Air Berau, and Lubuk Bento. Two accessions with a rounded base shape were found in two villages, namely Pondok Suguh and Pondok Kandang, while one accession with a cuneate base shape was recorded from Lubuk Bento (Figure 6).

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Figure 6. Leaf base shape: (a) Pondok Suguh (Oblique), (b) Air Berau (Rounded), (c) Lubuk Bento (Cuneate).

There were three types of fruit shapes: spheroid, ellipsoid, and irregular. The spheroid-shaped fruit was found in accessions from Pondok Kandang Village, the ellipsoid-shaped fruit from Tunggang Village, and the irregular-shaped fruit from Lubuk Bento Village. Each fruit exhibited a similar color, with slight variations among the jackfruit accessions (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Fruit shape: (a) Lubuk Bento (irregular), (b) Pondok Kandang (spheroid), (c) Tunggang (ellipsoid)

There were three types of fruit flesh shapes observed: twisted, rectangular, and irregular. The rectangular-shaped flesh was found in accessions from Pondok Kandang Village, the irregular-shaped flesh from Tunggang Village, and the twisted-shaped flesh from Lubuk Bento Village (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Fruit flesh shape: (a) Lubuk Bento (twisted), (b) Pondok Kandang (rectangular), (c) Tunggang (irregular)

There were three types of seed shapes: ellipsoid, reniform, and irregular. The ellipsoid-shaped seeds were found in accessions from Tunggang Village, the reniform-shaped seeds in accessions from Lubuk Bento Village, and the irregular-shaped seeds in accessions from Pondok Kandang Village (Figure 9).

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Figure 9. Seed shape: (a) Lubuk Bento Village (reniform), (b) Pondok Kandang Village (irregular), (c) Tunggang Village (ellipsoid)

Based on morphological characteristics, jackfruit in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency was classified into two groups. Group 1 consisted of accessions from Air Berau (AB), Lubuk Bento (LB), Karya Mulya (KM), and Tunggang (TGG). Group 2 included accessions from Pondok Suguh (PS) and Pondok Kandang (PK) (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Dendrogram of canopy shape, branching pattern, leaf shape, leaf apex shape, and petiole shape.

The canopy shapes of jackfruit trees showed phenotypic variation, including pyramidal, broadly pyramidal, elliptical, and irregular forms. Based on cluster analysis, the jackfruit trees were grouped into two main clusters. Group I included Air Berau (AB), Lubuk Bento (LB), Karya Mulya (KM), and Tunggang (TGG). Group II comprised of Pondok Suguh (PS) and Pondok Kandang (PK). A comprehensive summary of the qualitative and quantitative results is presented in Table 1

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Table 1. Characteristics of stem, leaf, fruit, and seed of jackfruit in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict, Mukomuko Regency

Characteristic	Group 1	Group 2
Canopy shape	Broadly pyramidal – semicircular – elliptical	Oblong – semicircular – irregular
Branching direction	Erect – opposite	Horizontal – irregular
Leaf blade shape	Broadly elliptic – narrowly elliptic	Elliptic – narrowly elliptic
Leaf apex shape	Acute – acuminate	Acute – acuminate
Leaf color	Green	Green
Petiole shape	Oblique	Oblique – rounded – cuneate
Fruit shape	Ellipsoid	Spheroid – ellipsoid
Fruit attachment	Flattened	Depressed – inflated
Fruit flesh shape	Spheroid – ellipsoid – cordate	Twisted – rectangular – irregular
Seed shape	Spheroid	Ellipsoid – reniform – irregular
Fruit skin color	Yellowish green	Yellowish green
Flesh color	Pale yellow – deep yellow	Deep yellow – copper red – pale yellow
Seed coat color	Pale white – cream	Pale white – cream – dull brown
Stem circumference (cm)	66–116	72–90
Leaf length (cm)	12–19	11–17
Leaf width (cm)	7–12	8–11
Fruit length (cm)	34–50	28–42
Fruit width (cm)	17–25	20–22
Fruit circumference (cm)	68–80	58–61
Fruit weight (kg)	7–10	5.7–8
Fruit firmness (kgf/cm ²)	10.7–12.6	10.5–12.4
Flesh weight (g)	560–706	452–675
Seed weight (g)	150–182	87–174
Rind weight (g)	560–632	457–620
Total rind weight (kg)	5–9	7–9
Core length (cm)	29–44	30–41

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Characteristic	Group 1	Group 2
Core width (cm)	7–15	8–14
Fruit skin thickness (mm)	1.3–1.9	1.5–1.8
Flesh thickness (mm)	0.3–0.6	0.4–0.5
Flesh width (cm)	1	1
Sugar content (°Brix)	15–23	10–16
Seed hardness (mld)	0.7–0.8	0.8–0.9
Fruit stalk length (cm)	6–12	8–11
Total number of seeds	64–124	46–136
Number of seeds per kg	19–36	16–33

DISCUSSION

These findings indicated morphological differences in fruit characteristics among jackfruit plants from Lubuk Bento, Pondok Kandang, and Tunggang Villages. The fruit shapes observed from the three jackfruit accessions in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict included one spheroid fruit from Pondok Kandang and two ellipsoid fruits from Lubuk Bento and Tunggang. The fruit skin color of the three accessions was the same, showing a yellowish-green hue, found in the accessions from Lubuk Bento, Pondok Kandang, and Tunggang Villages. The fruit weight ranged from 8 kg to 5.7 kg, with the heaviest fruit found in the Lubuk Bento accession. The fruit length ranged from 42 cm to 28 cm, with the longest fruit also found in the Lubuk Bento accession (Figure 7).

The fruit width among the three accessions ranged from 22 cm to 20 cm, with the widest fruit observed in the Pondok Kandang accession. The fruit circumference ranged from 61 cm to 58 cm, with the greatest circumference recorded in the Lubuk Bento accession. Fruit firmness ranged from 12.4 kgf to 10.5 kgf, with the firmest fruit found in the Tunggang accession. The jackfruit pulp length across the three accessions ranged from 8 cm to 5 cm, with the longest pulp found in the Lubuk Bento accession. Pulp width ranged from 1 cm to 0.5 cm, with the widest pulp observed in the Pondok Kandang accession (Figure 8).

The pulp color varied among the three accessions: deep yellow from Lubuk Bento, copper-red from Pondok Kandang, and pale yellow from Tunggang. The sugar content of the pulp ranged from 15 to 23 oBrix, with the highest sugar level recorded in the Pondok Kandang accession, commonly referred to as "Honey jackfruit" due to its sweetness. Pulp thickness ranged from 0.6 cm to 0.8 cm, with the thickest pulp found in the Pondok Kandang accession. It can be concluded that superior jackfruit pulp characteristics are mostly found in the Pondok Kandang accession (Figure 8).

Seed hardness of the three accessions showed little variation, ranging from 0.74 to 0.71 millimeters

divisions (mld). Three seed shape colors were observed: pale white from Tunggang, cream from Pondok Kandang, and dull brown from Lubuk Bento (Figure 9). The morphological differences observed in jackfruit plants in Pondok Suguh Subdistrict are attributed to genetic variation and differing environmental conditions across the accession origins. Factors such as soil conditions, microclimate, and local cultivation practices can influence morphological expression, including fruit shape, flesh color, and sugar content (Khan et al., 2021). This study was consistent with the findings of, who emphasized the importance of morphological and genetic characterization for identifying locally superior genotypes (Abdelkawy et al., 2024). It has been reported that environmental factors affect morphological and physiological traits in jackfruit, which aligns with the variation in sugar content and pulp color found among accessions in Mukomuko.

This diversity was crucial for germplasm conservation, as highlighted by (Dewi, 2021), in *Artocarpus* species from Kalimantan. Moreover, (Gladis et al., 2022), and (Hazarika et al., 2025), showed that differences in fruit and leaf morphology often reflect adaptations to local agroecological conditions. (Hossain et al., 2020), emphasized the nutritional and antioxidant value of jackfruit flesh and seeds, supporting the utilization of high sugar accessions such as that from Pondok Kandang. The morphological characterization standards used in this study referred to IPGRI (2000)(Palupi & Daryono, 2021), allowing for global data comparability. Structural fruit assessment and firmness, as evaluated by (Lazarus et al., 2023), further supported the significance of attributes such as flesh thickness and fruit firmness for agronomic and biomaterial purposes. (Simanjuntak et al., 2022) demonstrated the potential of jackfruit as a herbal medicinal resource, highlighting the need to develop varieties with high bioactive compound content for functional applications (Morelos-Flores et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

There was morphological diversity among jackfruit plants. Variations were observed in canopy shapes, including irregular, semicircular, elliptical, oblong, and broadly pyramidal, as well as in branching patterns, such as irregular, horizontal, opposite, and erect. Leaf blades exhibited three distinct shapes: narrowly elliptic, broadly elliptic, and elliptic, while leaf apices were classified into two types: acute and acuminate. In terms of fruit morphology, differences were found in leaf length and width, fruit weight, sugar content, and flesh shape.

The accession from Pondok Kandang Village exhibited the highest sugar content at 23 °Brix, with thick fruit flesh reaching 0.8 cm and an attractive copper-red color. The accession from Lubuk Bento Village showed the longest (50 cm) and heaviest (10 kg) fruits, with a sugar content of up to 21 °Brix. These results indicated that the morphological diversity of local jackfruit plants holds significant potential as a germplasm resource, which can be utilized in breeding programs to develop cultivars that are locally adaptive, resistant to pests and diseases, and possess high economic value.

SUGESTION

Obtaining ripe fruits during the research period posed a limitation due to the varying ripening times among trees. Identifying sample plants that met the predetermined criteria also presented challenges in acquiring representative data. An intensive personal approach was required with landowners where jackfruit trees were selected as data collection objects.

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